

Flow Behaviour of Chinaclay Suspension during Interaction with Certain Organic Polyions

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Interaction of kaolinitic type of clay with some water soluble organic polyions was studied in suspension form at room temperature. The modes of particle association caused by interaction were interpreted through rheological measurements.

THE stability of the clay suspension is very much dependent on the composition of the double layer which can be controlled by addition of extraneous ions. Although traditionally various inorganic compounds such as NaOH, Na₂CO₃, Na-silicate, aluminate, hexametaphosphates have been used as dispersing agent but there are studies relating to the effect of organic polyions on the rheological properties of clays¹. Because of the existence of a number of water-soluble polyelectrolytes and wide variation in the structure of clay minerals, there is tremendous scope to work out the actual mechanism of interaction as well as tailor made suspension for particular purpose. Present investigation is one such attempt to study the effect of several organic polyions differing in their molecularity, dissociation and complex forming capacities.

Experimental

Kerala Chinaclay, one of the widely used good variety of clay for white-ware industries was used. It was purified by following wet sedimentation technique and then converted to Na-form by repeated leaching with 0.5 M NaCl solution and dried. The pulverised sample was kept in an incubator (32 ± 1°).

The rheological measurements were carried out in a rotational cup and bob viscometer of McMichael model. Multipoint consistency curves were drawn from which yield value and plastic viscosity were calculated by utilising the Reiner and Rewlin equation²,

$$\Omega = \mu \cdot \frac{T}{4\pi h} \left(\frac{1}{R_b^2} - \frac{1}{R_c^2} \right) - \mu_t \ln \frac{R_c}{R_b} \quad (1)$$

where Ω is the angular viscosity, μ the viscosity, h the depth of immersion of the bob, T the movement due to external forces (torque), f the yield value, R_b and R_c are radii of the bob and cup respectively. For yield value,

$$f = CT_2 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Plastic viscosity } (U) = \frac{(T - T_2)S}{\Omega} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{where, } S = \frac{1}{R_b^2} - \frac{1}{R_c^2}, \quad C = \frac{S}{\ln \frac{R_c}{R_b}}$$

and $U = 1, \mu$

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analysis of purified Kerala Chinaclay in Na form are SiO₂, 46.5, Al₂O₃, 38.53; Fe₂O₃, 1.27; CaO, 0.43; MgO, 0.20; loss on ignition, 12.37%. The CEC, surface area and DTA peak temperatures are 3.58 meq/100 g, 22000 cm²/g and 530 (endo) and 980 (exo) respectively. The yield value and plastic viscosity of 20% chinaclay suspension without any addition were found to be 12.79 dyn/cm² and 65.14 × 10⁻³ poise respectively.

The change of yield value and plastic viscosity of 20% clay suspension as a function of organic polyions concentration are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

The physicochemical characteristics of the sample indicate the true kaolinitic nature. The surface area (22000 cm²/g) did not show appreciable departure from that of other chinaclay minerals. On the other hand, the clay appears to be slightly finer.

The rheological studies were conducted at a fixed clay concentration (20% w/v) where the suspension behaved in a non-Newtonian fashion. The object of taking this type of suspension is that most of the organic polyions are recognised to act as dispersing agents and the interaction is characterised by reduction of yield stress.

The nature of the flow curves was identical and did not exhibit any departure from non-Newtonian fluid and as such some of the representative curves have been shown in Fig. 3. Positive existence of yield value in the suspension during interaction indicates that in all the cases non-Newtonian nature was maintained. Except Na-carboxy methylcellulose in all other cases it was higher than that obtained without addition of any reagents. This might be due to particle association initiated by the modi-

fication of particle charge. For this reason the nature of yield value changes as a function of polyelectrolyte content, was not identical (Fig. 1). With the exception of Na-lauryl sulphate, the yield value exhibited a decreasing tendency on progressive addition of polyelectrolytes. In case of pentaerythretol the change was not much significant. At the final point of addition, the yield value was maximum with the pentaerythretol and minimum with Na-carboxymethylcellulose. The significant reduction of yield value with Na-CMC might be due to reduction of edge to face association through reversal of edge positive charge of clay minerals by complexation of Al-atom.

The change of plastic viscosity has been represented in Fig. 2. Except polyethylene oxide, reduction of plastic viscosity at the first point of addition of polyelectrolyte was observed and the difference was maximum with Na-CMC. The initial portion of the curves exhibited some similarity, i.e. viscosity initially increased, and after reaching a maximum, the plastic viscosity decreased indicating thereby that

Fig. 1. Plots of concentration vs yield value of 20% chinaclay suspension during interaction with organic polyions: (1) Na-CMC, (2) Na-polyacrylate, (3) Na-lauryl sulphate, (4) polyethylene oxide, (5) pentaerythretol and (6) methylcellulose.

Fig. 2. Plots of concentration vs plastic viscosity of 20% chinaclay suspension during interaction with organic polyions: (1) Na-CMC, (2) Na-polyacrylate, (3) Na-lauryl sulphate, (4) polyethylene oxide, (5) pentaerythretol and (6) methylcellulose.

the mechanism of interaction at least in this zone was same, i.e. lowering the magnitude of solvent solute interaction. It is to be mentioned here that in presence of polyelectrolyte not only the particle charge on clay is modified but the polarity of the dispersion medium is also altered. This viscosity change was quite significant and unlike yield value the variation was higher. At the final point of addition, maximum viscosity was exhibited by Na-lauryl sulphate and minimum by Na-CMC. The sequence of polyions with respect to variation of plastic viscosity has some similarity with that of the yield value although these two are different properties.

The molecularity of the polyions is one of the factors controlling partially the viscosity of the suspension. In some cases the interaction with clays may be retarded by the formation of a colloidal layer on the surface of the grains as exhibited by Na-polyacrylate and Na-CMC. Na-lauryl sulphate,

Fig. 3. Flow curves of 20% chinaclay suspension in presence of (a) 0.25% Na-CMC and (b) 0.25% Na-lauryl sulphate : (1) 0.5, (2) 2.5, (3) 5, (4) 7.5 and (5) 10 ml.

pentaerythritol and polyethylene oxide showed relatively high values of plastic viscosity throughout the entire range of addition than that obtained without any addition.

Thus by controlled addition of organic poly-electrolytes, both yield value and plastic viscosity of clay-based suspension can be adjusted to the desired value as required for particular purpose.

References

1. C KAJISAKI, K. HORI and Y. TANABE, *Bull Govt Res Inst. Ceram. (Kyoto)*, 1951, **5**, 71; I. H. JOYCE and W. E. WORALL, *Trans Br. Ceram Soc.*, 1963, 189; N. K. MITRA, A. C. DAS, A. BASUMAJUMDAR and T. K. PARYA, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 515; N. CELIK, I. H. MALTON and B. RAND, *Trans Br Ceram. Soc.*, 1988, **82**, 136.
2. H. GREEN, "Industrial Rheology and Rheological Structures", Wiley, New York, 1949, p 35